

**THE ROLE OF INDIVIDUAL CREATIVE TASKS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION AMONG STUDENTS MAJORING IN
ECONOMICS**

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Abstract. This article discusses the role and importance of individual creative tasks in the development of interpersonal communication among students studying economics. In the modern education system, one of the important tasks is to prepare students for independent thinking, effective teamwork, and professional communication. Individual creative tasks serve as an effective tool for developing students' communicative competence, forming a speech culture, and ensuring their adaptation to professional activity. The article scientifically substantiates the impact of presentations, project work, problem situations, and analytical tasks on students' communicative activity. It is also emphasized that tasks organized on the basis of a creative approach increase students' leadership skills, free thinking, and social activity.

Keywords: individual creative task, interpersonal communication, communicative competence, economics students, speech culture, creative thinking, interactive methods, professional communication, educational effectiveness, independent learning.

In today's era of globalization and increasing competition, the higher education system is faced with the task of training specialists with modern knowledge and skills. In particular, students studying in the field of economics must not only master theoretical knowledge, but also have the skills to effectively communicate, work in a team, negotiate, and express their opinions in a reasoned manner during their professional activities. Therefore, the development of students' interpersonal communication in the process of higher education is considered one of the important pedagogical issues.

Interpersonal communication is one of the most important factors in human social activity. Especially for specialists working in the field of economics, cooperation, establishing business relationships, solving problems with a team, and effective communication with clients are of great importance. Individual creative tasks serve as an effective tool in the formation of such competencies. Because creative tasks expand the student's ability to think independently, reason freely, and clearly convey their views to others[1].

While in the traditional educational process, students are more focused on mastering ready-made knowledge, modern pedagogical technologies require them to be active participants. In this regard, individual creative tasks develop students' independent activity and encourage them to search. Tasks such as preparing a presentation, developing a project, analyzing economic situations, creating a business plan, or expressing an opinion on problematic issues play an important role in developing students' communicative competence.

For example, the task of preparing a business project on the topic "Developing Youth Entrepreneurship" not only strengthens the student's economic knowledge, but also forms his speech culture and skills in working with the audience. While working on the project, the student collects information, analyzes it, develops his conclusions and conveys them to others through a presentation. This expands his thinking and helps him communicate freely in front of the team.

Also, individual creative tasks teach students to think creatively and critically. In economics, communicative activity plays an important role in analyzing various economic problems,

proposing solutions to them, and making decisions. Therefore, giving students assignments based on problem situations not only develops their analytical thinking, but also strengthens their communication skills.

Currently, the use of interactive methods is becoming widely popular in the higher education system. Individual assignments based on debates, brainstorming, case studies, presentations, and role-playing games make students active participants in the learning process. Through these methods, students exchange ideas with each other, discuss problems, and learn to defend their point of view.

This article scientifically analyzes the pedagogical potential of individual creative assignments in developing interpersonal communication among students of economics, their impact on educational effectiveness, and their role in the formation of communicative competence.

In the modern higher education system, one of the important tasks in the process of preparing students for professional activity is not only to impart theoretical knowledge, but also to develop their communicative competence. In particular, students studying in the field of economics will have to constantly communicate with various business partners, clients, investors, and team members in the future. Therefore, the formation of interpersonal communication skills in them is one of the urgent issues of modern pedagogy. In this regard, individual creative tasks are of particular importance as an effective pedagogical tool.

Individual creative tasks serve to develop the student's independent thinking, analytical approach, and creative abilities. Through such tasks, the student not only receives knowledge, but also acquires the skills of freely expressing his or her opinion, solving problems, collaborating with others, and conducting professional communication. The use of creative tasks in teaching subjects in the field of economics forms students as active participants.

Interpersonal communication is one of the important factors necessary for a person's social activity in society. It includes the ability of a person to listen, exchange ideas, ask questions, negotiate, and establish effective relationships with others. In the field of economics, communicative competence is one of the main conditions for successful work. Because an economist must be ready to discuss various economic issues, defend projects, and actively participate in business negotiations.

One of the main advantages of individual creative assignments is that they help to take into account the individual capabilities of each student. Each student thinks differently, and the way he perceives and expresses information is also unique. Therefore, efficiency increases when individual assignments are organized in accordance with the student's interests, abilities, and level of knowledge[3].

For example, students who are assigned to prepare a project on the topic "Small Business Development Strategies" can work in different directions. One student may focus on marketing strategy, while another will cover the issue of financial planning or the use of innovative technologies. Each student independently develops his own views and conveys them to the audience during the presentation. This develops their speech culture and communication skills.

The use of individual creative tasks in the educational process also forms the competence of students in independent learning. While working on the task, the student searches for scientific sources, analyzes data, draws conclusions and tries to justify his opinion. This process, in turn, strengthens his communicative activity.

For example, the task of writing an essay on the topic "Prospects for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan" requires the student to conduct extensive research. The student studies statistical data, analyzes foreign experiences and expresses his conclusions in written and

oral form. As a result of such tasks, the student develops the skills of thinking in a scientific manner and communicating with the audience.

Today, individual tasks organized on the basis of interactive methods are of great importance in increasing the effectiveness of education. Methods such as debates, “brainstorming”, “case studies”, “SWOT analysis” encourage students to think actively and increase communicative activity.

For example, a debate could be organized on the topic “The Impact of Inflation on the Economy.” Students are divided into two groups and express their opinions on the positive and negative aspects of inflation. Each student provides evidence to support their point of view and analyzes opposing views. In the process, they develop the skills of free thinking, questioning, and debating.

Individual creative assignments also play an important role in developing leadership skills in students. During a presentation, project defense, or business idea presentation, a student learns to manage the audience and confidently defend his or her opinion.

For example, the task of preparing a presentation on the topic “New Business Startup Project” requires the student not only economic knowledge, but also communication skills. The student will need to clearly explain the project’s purpose, financial plan, and expected results. Answering questions from the audience during the presentation will further develop his or her communication skills.

The use of role-playing games in developing interpersonal communication among students majoring in economics also gives effective results. Through role-playing games, students model real-life economic situations and gain practical communication experience[2].

For example, a role-playing game is organized on the topic “Bank and Client”. One student plays the role of a bank employee, and the other plays the role of a client. The client applies for a loan, and the bank employee explains the loan terms to him. During this process, students acquire the skills of speaking in a formal style, listening, and answering questions clearly.

In addition, individual creative assignments also develop students' critical thinking. Critical thinking allows for a deep analysis of economic processes and a look at problems from different perspectives. This increases the effectiveness of communicative activities.

For example, a student is assigned to write an analytical article based on the question “Why do some business projects fail?” The student studies various reasons, gives examples, and develops his own proposals. Then the article is discussed. This encourages students to engage in debate.

Modern information and communication technologies also increase the effectiveness of individual assignments. Nowadays, students prepare presentations, create video lessons, and participate in virtual conversations through online platforms. This serves to form their modern communicative culture.

For example, a student is assigned to prepare a video presentation on the topic “Advantages of e-commerce”. During the preparation of the video, the student works on the speech, systematically presents the information and tries to convey it to the audience in an understandable way. As a result, the student develops creativity along with communicative competence.

Individual creative tasks also prepare students for working in a team. Although the task is completed individually, during its presentation and discussion, students listen to each other's opinions and interact. This serves the development of interpersonal communication.

The teacher's pedagogical skills also play an important role in developing students' communicative competence. The teacher must organize individual tasks taking into account the

age and psychological characteristics of the students. At the same time, supporting and encouraging students' creative ideas increases communicative activity[1].

For example, if the teacher gives positive feedback after the student's presentation and gently explains his shortcomings, the student will strive to participate more actively next time. This strengthens his self-confidence.

In conclusion, it can be said that individual creative tasks are one of the effective tools for developing interpersonal communication among students majoring in economics. They develop students' independent thinking, speech culture, leadership skills, and professional competence. Also, through individual tasks, students acquire the skills of analyzing modern economic problems, working in a team, and conducting professional communication.

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